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PRECEDENT PRODUCT FORM STYLES OF ULTRA-SLIM COMPACT DIGITAL CAMERA SERIES OF DIFFERENT BRANDS

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ABSTRACT

This study explored how designers manipulate precedent serial product forms. From user's points of view, the roles different design elements and their form treatments play in the product form styles were analyzed. The semantic differential (SD) experiments were undertaken to gather the consumers' perceptions and purchase intentions towards serial product forms so as to uplift the quality of product design. Product image samples of Canon IXUS, Sony T, and Nikon COOLPIX series from 2003 to 2010 were collected for the perceptual and purchase intention tests. Results from different brands of ultra-slim compact digital cameras are compared in terms of product form design. From the distribution patterns of product form styles of ultra-slim digital cameras of Canon, Sony, and Nikon, there is an increase tendency in all styles of images. At last, important design elements of product form to enhance the purchase intention are discussed.

Keywords: product form, precedent products, purchase intention, Kansei engineering

INTRODUCTION

In the market of mature products whose life span has changed to a much shorter period of time, e.g., electronic commodity, two policies regarding product design can be adopted: serial design or product differentiation (Chang and Wu, 2009). In most redesign cases, products of the same brand or a series of products at different periods of time can be connected by some similar features to maintain existing customers' loyalty (Storbacka et al., 1994). In other words, they should look similar to each other with certain product or brand images so that

consumers may consider them products of the same group. In the product differentiation policy (Kotler and Kevin, 2006), a product from one company should look different from its counterparts of other companies. In this study, the authors explored the unique styles of three different digital camera brands in recent years through different clues from quantitative experiments. From the quantitative evaluation of product form styles, the design trends of consumer digital camera design for three different brands were investigated. Then, based upon the consumers' intention of purchase, product design and development strategies for ultra-slim compact digital camera are suggested.

In the consumerism era today, consumers' needs and voices should be satisfied through the commodity. To guarantee the success of a product in the market place, many scholars claim that the style or image of product form is a soft function and can help fulfill customers' expectations. Because the product image is composed of all design elements, different product images may indicate different forms and furthermore correspond to different patterns of design elements. Many researchers have dealt with the relationships between images and form features (for example, Hsiao and Chen, 2006; Chuang et al., 2001; Chuang and Ma, 2001). At the design house or design department in an enterprise, designers need to work out a proper design specification for design project. In this document, the product styling plan is a key element in that it will pinpoint the direction and expected product style for the target users. According to Baxter (1995), there are four main categories of contextual styling factors: product predecessors, company or brand identities, competing product styling, style benchmarking. In serial products, the perceived similarity between a

particular product and its previous generations of products may moderate the consumers' responses (Crilly et al., 2003). If the proposed new product is an update of an existing product currently sold by the company, then it is important to preserve the visual identity of the product (Baxter, 1995). In this way, the existing customers will continue to recognize the product and purchase it again. It is an important product design strategy that serial products have common features to help communicate the identity or brand image in an enterprise.

To collect consumers' perceptions and purchase intentions toward serial product forms, three leaders in Taiwan's market of ultra-slim digital cameras were used as examples in SD experiments. With the data obtained from the experiment, the design trends and form treatments of these digital camera brands were analyzed.

METHOD

The SD experiments conducted in this study were divided into the pilot test and the SD experiment on a 7-point Likert scale. In the pilot test, 16 subjects with design background were first invited to evaluate 32 digital cameras from which 10 image words and intention of purchase were selected for the SD test. Subjects: 150 students with design background and experience of using digital cameras were invited for the image and purchase intention evaluation. Experimental materials: From their launch time in Taiwan till 2010, 36 ultra-slim compact of digital cameras including 16 Canon IXUS series, 12 Sony T series, and 8 Nikon COOLPIX series were used with the codes of C01~C16, S01~S12, N01~N08 respectively. In the test, the front and back views of digital cameras were printed on color A5-size hard copies with their logos.

Unimaginative -Creative	Traditional-Fashionable
Inelegant-Elegant	Heavy-Compact
Complex-Simple	Popular-Individualized
Square-Streamlined	Plain-Luxury
Coarse-Delicate	Unattractive-Attractive
Intention of purchase	

Table 1 Image pairs used in the SD experiment

Procedure: The SD experiment was conducted in the individual way. The subjects were asked to evaluate the product sample images according to their first impressions of the specific image (Table 1). To reduce the mental workload, they were asked to do the test in their own pace and each subject took about one hour in the evaluation.

Semantic scale: The experiment was conducted on a 7-pointed Likert scale with 7 points for the extreme degree of the right side image word and 1 point for the extreme degree of the left side image word. For the intention of purchase, 7 means that the subject was fully willing to buy the product sample while 1 means the least intention of purchase.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Product form styles of Canon IXUS, Sony T, and Nikon COOLPIX series

Figure 1 illustrates the scatter diagrams of Canon IXUS, Sony T, Nikon COOLPIX series in average image scores. In total images, Canon IXUS series and Sony T series are evident in elegant, compact, streamlined, individualized, and attractive images. In the scatter diagrams of average images, Canon IXUS series falls behind Sony T series and Nikon COOLPIX series in every image, while Sony T series and Nikon COOLPIX series are similar to each other. Averagely speaking, Nikon COOLPIX series and Sony T series are very similar in image perceptions and they can be looked upon as a group. Canon IXUS series is another group. For most images, Nikon COOLPIX series and Sony T series had an average >4.5 while Canon IXUS series <4.5.

In addition to the average image scores, the percentage of high, moderate, and low images in product samples in three brands is calculated (Tables 2, 3, 4). From the percentage data of digital camera series, these three brands of ultra-slim compact cameras are evident in delicate image. Sony T series leads in creative, fashionable, luxury, and delicate images. Nikon COOLPIX series leads in compact and simple images. Canon IXUS are considered less evident than Sony T series and Nikon COOLPIX series in all images. Particularly, all three series of Sony, Canon, and Nikon are low in streamlined image because of their rectangular product forms.

Figure 1. The scatter diagrams of Canon IXUS, Sony T, Nikon COOLPIX series in average image scores

Image words	Canon IXUS series		Sony T series		Nikon COOLPIX series	
	% of high image (>5.0)	Avg image score	% of high image (>5.0)	Avg image score	% of high image (>5.0)	Avg image score
Creative	1/16 (6.25%)	3.69	5/12 (41.67%)	4.93	2/8 (25%)	4.73
Fashionable	3/16 (18.75%)	3.86	8/12 (66.67%)	5.27	3/8 (37.5%)	4.92
Luxury	2/16 (12.5%)	3.81	7/12 (58.33%)	5.08	3/8 (37.5%)	4.79
Elegant	3/16 (18.75%)	4.24	8/12 (66.67%)	5.12	5/8 (62.5%)	5.17
Compact	0	3.54	2/12 (16.67%)	4.56	3/8 (37.5%)	4.73
Delicate	5/16 (31.25%)	4.33	7/12 (58.33%)	5.38	5/8 (62.5%)	5.15
Streamlined	0	3.31	0	3.88	0	3.92
Simple	1/16 (6.25%)	3.95	6/12 (50%)	5.13	6/8 (75%)	5.27
Individualized	0	3.70	4/12 (33.33%)	4.80	2/8 (25%)	4.80
Attractive	1/16 (6.25%)	3.67	7/12 (58.33%)	4.98	2/8 (25%)	4.87

Table 2. % of high images and average image scores of Canon IXUS series digital cameras

Figure 2. 3 Clusters of Canon IXUS series

DIGITAL CAMERA CLUSTERS IN THE SAME BRAND

To explore the subtle change of form treatments and design trends for product series in the same company, cluster analyses were conducted. For each brand, three clusters of digital cameras were specified (Figures 2, 3, 4). Basically, they are divided roughly by the time they were launched in the market place. For Canon IXUS Series, Cluster C1 consists of Samples C01, C02, C03, C04; they are from 2000/01 - 2002/08. Cluster C2 is made up of Samples C05, C06, C07, C08, C09, C10; 2003/05 - 2006/02. Cluster C3 is composed of Samples C12, C13, C14, C15, C16; 2007/02 - 2010/02.

With the combination of rounded rectangle and coaxial circles, Canon IXUS series reflects compact, elegant, and undertone styles. From the tree diagram of the clusters of Canon IXUS series (Figure 2), the four product samples in Cluster C1 were the earlier versions of ultra-slim compact digital cameras. They are of small sized screen, less functions, simple control buttons, and regular rectangles. From C02 to C03, a cross-shaped five direction control button is added and the logo is separated from the wrist strap. Compared with products in 2000 and 2001, Canon IXUS series in 2002 adds a shiny silvery color in the body, no more only of the traditional champagne gold. The circles around the lens shrink. Furthermore, the addition of the cross-shaped control button makes it easier to operate.

In seven samples in Cluster C2 of Canon IXUS series, multiple functions have been developed, resulting in more control buttons and bigger screens. From sample C04 to C05, the shape of mode selector is changed from the horizontal push type to circular dial knobs and it is different in the combination of logo and wrist strap. After C07, radical changes in product form were added, especially in the lens rings. In sample C08, the lens rings are changed from planar to concave-convex style. Instead of protruding style, the wrist strap is hidden in the body. Of the consistent locations, the control buttons are enlarged in continuous circles. Different from C08, the lens ring color of C09 is dark gray. From C09 to

C10, the lens ring is changed to planar type with the same color of the body; a bigger 2.5 inch LCD screen, a vertical push mode selector, and a circular viewing port with half an edge cut are offered. In C11, the lens rings are three-dimensional; the mode selector and speaker exchange their location; a protruding wrist strap is again added.

The five product samples of Cluster C3 of Canon IXUS series were launched in Taiwan market in 2007. Sample C12 is similar to the earlier Canon IXUS series, with a special rectangular product form, making it more delicate and sleek. Since 2008, the body is no more of regular rectangle. Instead, a curved design can be seen. In addition, chromate treatment is added in the circular rings of lens with a more fashionable color. Different from C12, C13 features a non-planar lens ring and a curved total image. The product forms of C13 to C16 feature a more evident curve with a slenderer body and neat buttons.

For Sony T series, Cluster S1 is made up of Samples S01, S03, S04, S05; 2003/11 - 2005/03. Cluster S2 contains Samples S02, S06, S07; 2004/04 - 2005/11. Cluster S3 is composed of Samples S08, S09, S10, S11, S12; 2006/08 - 2008/09. Sony digital cameras always give people special images of design, fashion, and compact. Among many popular digital camera series, users have a strong impression on Sony's sliding consumer digital cameras through it is not originally invented by Sony. Nevertheless, since T1 entered the market, the sliding digital camera seems a stereotype of Sony Cyber-Shot T series.

Among four samples of Cluster S1, S01 was launched in 2003, featuring rounded rectangular lines and standard control buttons. The lens caps of S03 and S04 are built inside. In S03, the shape of the wrist strap is changed and the control button is changed from the open cross-shape to a closed style. Different from S03, S04 features the arcs on the sides of the body. The direction button of S05 is put on the left side. A lot different from S04, S05 adds the typical Sony sliding lens cap and a flat wrist strap and places the control buttons on the left side of the LCD screen.

Figure 3. 3 Clusters of Sony T series

Figure 4. 3 Clusters of Nikon COOLPIX series

Cluster S2 of Sony T series contains S02, S06, and S07 in 2004-2006. All of them feature an evident curved form and a cross-shaped button on the right side. Different from S01, S02 doesn't have the sliding switch but has a larger wrist strap. Furthermore, S02 is no more of a rectangular shape. Instead, many curves are adopted on the edges. In S06 and S07, the sliding lens cap is enlarged; the control button is put back to the right side of LCD screen; the wrist strap is shrunk. Cluster S3 of Sony T series covers five samples of 2007-2010. With mature development of digital technology, most products at this period of time boast the touch screen. Moreover, a full scale lens cap can be found in these samples. In S08, the sliding switch is even bigger; a mask is added for the LCD screen; the cross-shaped control button is changed to an open design. Furthermore, the front view of S08 adopts evident curvatures along the sides. After S09, a neat and tidy form can be seen because of the touch screen. Besides the technology of touch screen, the major parts of form treatments in Sony T series lie in the sliding power switch and

the wrist strap. The sliding power switch appeared in S01 and is not adopted until S05. Its shapes vary in all samples. In addition, the adoption of hair line in the finish of the sliding power switch is another feature in Sony T series to uplift the luxury image. At last, the larger screen design makes it delightful for users to operate the Sony T series digital cameras.

Cluster N1 is made up of Samples N01, N02, N03; 2005/03-2005/09. Cluster N2 is composed of Samples N04, N05, N06; 2006/02-2006/08. Cluster N3 comprises Samples N07, N08; 2008/08-2009/08. Since 2005, Nikon COOLPIX series has been very popular in the market sector of ultra slim digital cameras for its compact style. Particularly, the famous S curve can be seen after the release of Nikon COOLPIX S5 in 2006, a prominent form feature in this series. Generally speaking, the change of product form in Nikon COOLPIX series is focused upon the anti-slippery on the right corner of the back, the integration style of the lens and flash light, and the screen.

Figure 5. The distribution patterns of clusters of Canon digital cameras

Figure 6. The distribution patterns of clusters of Sony digital cameras

Figure 7. The distribution patterns of clusters of Nikon digital cameras

The three samples in Cluster N1 are earliest versions of Nikon COOLPIX series. Their product forms are made up of rounded rectangles and the similar control buttons. N02 is different from N01 in its sliding lens cap, cut-edge design in the lens and flash light, and the masked LCD screen. In N03, the sliding power switch is cancelled. It is of circular design, just like N01 in the lens and flash light. Samples N04 to N06 are about the same in the product form, with the cross-shaped direction button on the right, circular lens and the hidden lens cap. Compared with N03, there is no rounded angle in N04 and the curvature in N04's body is more evident. The layout of buttons and the cross-shaped direction button are clearer in N04. In other words, N04 is sharper than N03, with a more protruding wrist strap and integral design of the flash and lens. The horizontal anti-slippery groove is changed to vertical design and an independent mode selector is added. N05 is almost identical to N04 except the bigger gap from the control knob. In N06, the anti-slippery design in the rear view is changed to the fan-shape and two buttons in the

middle are placed in the lower part of the body, giving it a neat and tidy look. N07 and N08 feature the touch screen and rounded rectangular lens. N07 is the first product in Nikon COOLPIX series that has the touch screen. Only the LCD screen and mask are seen in the back view. The body and lens frame of N07 are rectangular and separated from the flash light. On the lower left part of the front body, there is a metallic decoration, reflecting its high-tech and modern images. With the touch screen, most control buttons are gone. At last, the asymmetrical lines and rectangular lens frame in N07 as well as the special texture in N08 create the individualized image in Nikon ultra slim series digital camera.

Total image change of ultra-slim digital cameras

It is clear that, in all three brands of ultra slim digital cameras, there is an uprising tendency in the perceptual images with the passing by of years. This also increases the subjects' purchase intention. For Canon IXUS series, a bigger change of images can be seen in the periods of 2001-2002 and 2007-2008,

with an average difference bigger than 0.6 in all images, particularly in creative, fashionable, elegant, compact, and delicate images (refers to Figure 5).

To compare the differences of samples in different clusters, ANOVAs were conducted. Results demonstrated that in most product styles, there existed significant differences among different clusters. In the case of Canon IXUS series, there exist significant differences among three clusters in all image words except simple style. In terms of simple style of product form, Cluster1 C1 and C2 are about the same, but there is a significant difference between Cluster C3 and Clusters C1 and C2.

The uprising tendency in image perceptions can also be seen in Sony T series. Unlike radical fluctuations in Canon COOLPIX series, it is more stable in Sony T series. Except compact and streamlined images, Sony COOLPIX series improves each year in image perceptions and intention of purchase. From ANOVAs, significant differences can be found among three clusters in creative, fashionable, luxury, elegant, compact, delicate, attractive, and individualized images. However, no significant difference is found among three clusters in streamlined image. In simple image, no significant difference between Clusters S1 and S2 but there exists a significant difference between Clusters S3 and S1 as well as between Clusters S3 and S2. Similar to Sony T series, Nikon COOLPIX series rises each year in the image perceptions and purchase intention except the streamlined image. A lot of improvements can be seen in creative, fashionable, luxury, and individualized images. Particularly, Nikon COOLPIX series has the highest purchase intention from the subjects. From ANOVAs, significant differences can be found among three clusters in fashionable, luxury, elegant, delicate, simple, and individualized images. No significant difference exists between Clusters N1 and N2 but there exists a significant difference between Cluster N3 and Clusters N1 & N2 in creative and attractive images. In terms of compact and streamlined images, no significant difference is found between Clusters N2 and N3 but there exists a significant difference between Cluster N1 and Clusters N2 & N3.

UTILITIES OF FORM TREATMENTS TO PURCHASE INTENTION OF DIGITAL CAMERAS

In the study, Q-Type I analysis was conducted based on the average scores of purchase intention and morphological analysis of product form of digital cameras. From Q-Type I analysis, partial correlation coefficients reflect the relative importance of design elements of digital camera product form and the categorical weights indicate the influences of form treatments on subject's purchase intention.

With the morphological chart coding and purchase intention of 16 digital cameras of Canon IXUS series, partial correlation coefficients for design elements reflect the relative importance of design elements. The ranking order of relative importance of design elements in Canon IXUS series is screen (0.8809) > wrist strap (0.8410) > control buttons (0.7929) > viewing port (0.7849) > mode selector (0.5951) > lens frame (0.4981) > body (0.4525) > flash light (0.0158).

Furthermore, the category weights reflect the utilities of form treatments of design elements (Table 3). Significantly positive form treatments for high intention of purchase include independent rectangular screen (b3, 1.2459), without wrist strap (f3, 0.8355), separated circular control buttons (c2, 0.6414), circular with one edge cut viewing port (g2, 1.3348), circular with two edges cut viewing port (g3, 0.9126), straight push type mode selector (h2, 0.9765), and circular lens frame (d2, 0.8182). On the contrary, significantly negative form treatments for high intention of purchase are rectangular screen combined with control buttons (b1, -1.0027), semi-circular wrist strap (f1, -1.2746), special control buttons (c3, -1.2746), circular viewing port (g1, -0.6008), circular dial mode selector (h3, -0.4589), and rectangular body (a2, -1.1515). To guarantee that the users have higher intention of purchase, designers need to take consideration the form treatments highly positive and negative to subjects' purchase intention.

In the similar way, relative importance of design elements for the purchase intention and utilities of form treatments of Sony Cyber-shot T series and Nikon COOLPIX series are calculated.

Design elements	Patterns of design elements	Category weight	Partial correlation coefficients
A. Body	a1 Rounded rectangular	-0.1919	0.4525
	a2 Rectangular	-1.1515	
B. Screen	b1 Rectangular (with control)	-1.0027	0.8809
	b2 Rectangular (with viewing)	0.4557	
	b3 Independent rectangular	1.2459	
C. Control buttons	c1 Continuous circular	0.2029	0.7929
	c2 Separated circular	0.6414	
	c3 Special pattern	-1.2746	
D. Lens frame	d1 Circular (in the same plane)	-0.3273	0.4981
	d2 Circular (in an irregular plane)	0.8182	
E. Flash light	e1 Rectangular	-0.0164	0.0158
	e2 Trapezoid	0.0164	
F. Wrist strap	f1 Semi-circular	-1.2746	0.8410
	f2 Circular with one edge cut	0.0213	
	f3 Without wrist strap	0.8355	
G. Viewing port	g1 Circular	-0.6008	0.7849
	g2 Circular with one edge cut	1.3348	
	g3 Circular with two edges cut	0.9126	
H. Mode selector	h1 Horizontal push type	-0.3735	0.5951
	h2 Straight push type	0.9765	
	h3 Circular dial button	-0.4589	

Table 3 Utilities for design elements of Canon Digital IXUS series in the promotion of purchase intention

For Sony Cyber-shot T series, the ranking order of relative importance of design elements is mode selector (0.8119) > control buttons (0.6958) > screen (0.5977) > lens (0.5532) > wrist strap (0.3923) > lens cap (0.3239) > body (0.1865). For special form treatments, significantly positive form treatments for high intention of purchase include rectangular touch screen (b2, 0.8061), touch type control buttons (c3, 0.8061), independent mode selector

(g3, 0.9061), and touch type mode selector (g4, 0.5061). Furthermore, significantly negative form treatments for intention of purchase include closed circular cross control buttons (c2, -0.3130), square type of lens (d3, -0.8273), straight type mode selector (g2, -0.5023).

For Nikon COOLPIX Series, the ranking order of relative importance of design elements for the promotion of purchase intention is lens frame (0.9491) = control buttons (0.9491) > mode selector (0.8953) > lens cap (0.8849) = wrist strap (0.8849) = lens (0.8849) > screen (0.7710) > body (0.6843) > flash light (0.4712). For utilities of form patterns, significantly positive form treatments for high intention of purchase cover rectangular touch screen (b2, 0.6000), touch type control buttons (c3, 1.0333), rectangular lens (d3, 1.0333), rectangular sliding lens cap (e1, 1.0333), rectangular lens frame (f2, 1.0333), rectangular wrist strap (h1, 1.0333), and touch type mode selector (i3, 1.0333). Significantly negative form treatments for high intention of purchase include rounded rectangular body (a1, -0.3889), integral circular control buttons (c1, -0.3889), horizontal sliding type mode selector (i1, -0.3667), circular with edge-cut lens (d2, -0.4333), rectangular built-in lens cap (e2, -0.4333), without lens frame (f3, -0.3889), circular flash light (g1, -0.3667), and without wrist strap (h3, -0.4333). To make sure that the consumers have higher intentions of purchase towards new products of a company, designers need to pay more attention to the form treatments highly positive and negative to subjects' purchase intention.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

At the present study, product image samples of Canon IXUS, Sony T, and Nikon COOLPIX series from 2000 to 2010 were collected for the perceptual and purchase intention evaluations. Results from different brands of consumer digital cameras are compared and contrasted to construct the design and development strategies for new product design. From the distribution patterns of product form styles of ultra-slim compact digital cameras of these companies, there is an increase tendency in all styles of images for these brands. Furthermore, the elegant, delicate, and simple styles are the major

design strategies for all three brands of ultra-slim compact digital cameras. Results of cluster analysis demonstrated that, in about every three years, there would be a remarkable change of product form style in product form styles of ultra-slim compact digital cameras. In the same series, there is no remarkable difference in product form.

Average speaking, Nikon COOLPIX are similar to Sony T series, but they are quite different from Canon IXUS series. In the image scattering diagrams, product samples in Sony T series are close to those of Nikon COOLPIX series while samples of Canon IXUS series fall behind in virtually all product images. At last, results of Q-type I analyses of subjects' purchase intention indicated that for Canon IXUS series, the important design elements of product form include the screen, wrist strap, control buttons, and the viewing port. For Sony T series, the screen, control buttons, and mode selector are relatively more important design elements. Finally, to increase the intention of purchase, designers should pay more attention to the lens, control buttons, mode selector, lens cap, and wrist strap for Nikon COOLPIX series.

In the future, current and precedent commodities of different types of products can be further investigated. Perceptions from different user groups of consumer are another issue to explore.

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